

Nonlinear Programming: Theories and Algorithms of Some Unconstrained Optimization Methods (Steepest Descent and Newton's Method)

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ABSTRACT

Nonlinear programming problem (NPP) had become an important branch of operations research, and it was the mathematical programming with the objective function or constraints being nonlinear functions. There were a variety of traditional methods to solve nonlinear programming problems such as bisection method, gradient projection method, the penalty function method, feasible direction method, the multiplier method. But these methods had their specific scope and limitations, the objective function and constraint conditions generally had continuous and differentiable request. The traditional optimization methods were difficult to adopt as the optimized object being more complicated. However, in this paper, mathematical programming techniques that are commonly used to extremize nonlinear functions of single and multiple (n) design variables subject to no constraints are been used to overcome the above challenge. Although most structural optimization problems involve constraints that bound the design space, study of the methods of unconstrained optimization is important for several reasons. Steepest Descent and Newton's methods are employed in this paper to solve an optimization problem.

Keywords-- Nonlinear Programming Problem, Unconstrained Optimization, Mathematical Programming, Newton's Method, Steepest Descent

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I. INTRODUCTION

Analysts of operations research, managers, engineers of all kinds and planner faced by problems which needs to be solve. These problems may imply arriving at an optimal design, finding the flight of a jet etc. For example, in the engineering design, because there was no continuity in competition so therefore, it was communal to include a large safety factor. Now that there is continuity in competition, it is no longer capable to develop only an acceptable design. In other instance, such as in engineering motorcycle design, the development may be limited. Hence we ask questions like: can we find a more economical design? Are we making use of the scarce resources

effectively? Are we taking risk within the bankable limits? In response to all these, there has been a very rapid growth of optimization techniques and models.

The acceptance of the field of operations research in the study of business, and industrial activities can be attributed, at least in part, to the extent to which the operations research methods and approach have aided the decision makers. The application of operations research in the early post-war was mainly in the area of linear programming and use of statistics. Linear programming (LP) is used to find the most accurate outcomes (such as minimum cost or maximum profit) in a mathematical model whose requirements are imaged by linear relationships. Linear programming and nonlinear programming (NLP) are both similar in that it is compose of an objective function, general constraint, and (NLP) includes at least one nonlinear function, which could be the objective function, or some or all of the constraints.

Many real systems are inherently nonlinear, for example: the fall in signal strength or power with distance from the transceiver (antenna), so therefore, it is important that optimization algorithms be able to handle them.

In mathematics, nonlinear programming (NLP) is the process of solving an optimization problem defined by a system of equalities and inequalities, collectively termed constraints, over a set of unknown real variables, along with an objective function to be maximized or minimized, where some of the constraints or the objective function are nonlinear. It is the sub-field of Mathematical optimization that deals with problems that are not linear. (Wikipedia.). However, in this paper, unconstrained optimization is been considered and discussed.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

In time past, engineers, operations researchers, managers, etc were faced with problems to be solved. Some of these problems can be modelled into mathematical functions or equations which might not be linear (nonlinear systems of equations) and may be subject to some constraints or no constraints (unconstraint). Nonlinear programming approach can be employed to solve such mathematical equations. Here, we are looking at problems that involve nonlinear equations that are not subjected to

constraints by applying two unconstrained optimization methods, Steepest Descent method and Newton's method and compare results.

1.2 Aim and Objective

Aim of the Study

- The aim is to solve unconstrained optimization problem using Steepest Descent and Newton's method and comparing the behaviour of their result in terms of rate of convergence and degree of accuracy.

Objectives of the Study

- The objective is to do a proper study of unconstrained optimization problem studying two methods which is Steepest Descent and Newton's method
- To solve an example using the two methods and compare the results

1.3 Significance of the Study

Unconstrained optimization is important for the following reasons:

- If the design is at a stage where no constraints are active then the process of determining a search direction and travel distance for minimizing the objective function involves an unconstrained function minimization algorithm. Of, course in such a case one has constantly to watch for constraint violations during the move in design space.
- A constrained optimization problem can be cast as an unconstrained minimization problem even if the constraints are active.
- Unconstrained minimization strategies are becoming increasingly popular as techniques suitable for linear and nonlinear structural analysis problems which involve solution of a system of linear or nonlinear equations.

1.4 Limitations of the Study

The problem in nonlinear programming is that nonlinear models are much more difficult to optimize. Some of the problems are listed below:

- Numerical methods for solving nonlinear programs have limited information about the current point.
- Different algorithms and methods arrive at different solutions and outcome.
- Different but equivalent formulations of the model given to the same solver may produce different solution and outcomes.
- Different starting point may lead to different final solution.
- It may be difficult to find a feasible starting point.
- There is no finite determination of the outcome.

- It is difficult to determine whether the conditions to apply a particular method are met. (Chinneck, 2012)

1.5 Definition of Some Terms

Unconstrained optimization: Unconstrained optimization is an optimization that is subject to no constraints. Such problems may contain one or N variables.

Univariate: Problems with a single variable are called univariate. The univariate optimum for $Y = f(x)$ occurs at points where the first derivative of $f(x)$ with respect to $x(f'(x))$ equals zero. However, points which have zero first derivatives do not necessarily constitute a minimum or maximum. The second derivative is used to discover character of a point. Points at which a relative minimum occurs have a positive second derivative at that point while relative maximum occurs at points with a negative second derivative. Zero second derivatives are inconclusive.

It is important to distinguish between local and global optima. A local optimum arises when one finds a point whose value in the case of a maximum exceeds that of all surrounding points but may not exceed that of distant points. The second derivative indicates the shape of functions and is useful in indicating whether the optimum is local or global. The second derivative is the rate of change in the first derivative. If the second derivative is always negative (positive) that implies that any maximum (minimum) found is a global result. Consider a maximization problem with a negative second derivative for which $f'(x^*) = 0$. This means the first derivative was > 0 for $x < x^*$ and was < 0 for $x > x^*$. The function can never rise when moving away from X^* because of the sign of the second derivative. An everywhere positive second derivative indicates a global minimum will be found if $f'(x^*) = 0$, while a negative indicates a global maximum.

Multivariate functions: The univariate optimization results have multivariate analogues. In the multivariate case, partial derivatives are used, and a set of simultaneous conditions is established. The first and second derivatives are again key to the optimization process, excepting now that a vector of first derivatives and a matrix of second derivatives is involved.

There are several terms to review. First, the gradient vector, ∇ , is the vector of first order partial derivatives of a multivariate function with respect to each of the variables evaluated at the point.

$$\nabla(fx^0)_j = \left[\frac{\partial f(x^0)}{\partial x_j} \right] \quad (1.0)$$

where;

$\frac{\partial f(x^0)}{\partial x_j}$ Stands for the partial derivative of $f(X)$ with respect to X_j . The second derivatives constitute the Hessian matrix,

$$H(x^0)_{ij} = \left[\frac{\partial^2 f(x^0)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right] \quad (1.1)$$

The Hessian matrix, evaluated is an N by N symmetric matrix of second derivatives of the function with respect to each variable pair.

The multivariate version of the second derivative test involves examination of the Hessian matrix. If the Hessian matrix is neither positive nor negative definite, then no conclusion can be made about whether this point is a maximum or minimum and one must conclude it is an inflection or saddle point. (McCarl, 2010).

II. NONLINEAR PROGRAMMING

The paper that first used the name 'nonlinear programming' was written 41 years ago.

In the intervening period, there were a number of things about the influences, both mathematical and social, that have shaped the modern development of the subject. Some of these are quite old and long predate the differentiation of nonlinear programming as a separate area for research. Others are comparatively modern and culminate in the period 41 years ago when this differentiation took place. Tucker, (1997).

2.1 Basic Concepts of Optimization Methods

Optimization problems can be classified based on the type of constraints, nature of design variables, physical structure of the problem, nature of the equations involved, deterministic nature of the variables, permissible value of the design variables, separability of the functions and number of objective functions. These classifications are briefly discussed below.

2.1.1 Classification Based on Existence of Constraints

Under this category optimizations problems can be classified into two groups as follows:

Constrained Optimization Problems: which are subject to one or more constraints.

Unconstrained Optimization Problems: in which no constraints exist.

2.1.2 Classification Based on the Nature of the Design Variables

There are two broad categories in this classification.

(i) In the first category the objective is to find a set of design parameters that makes a prescribed function of these parameters minimum or maximum subject to certain constraints. For example to find the minimum weight design of a strip footing with two loads shown in Fig 1 (a) subject to a limitation on the maximum settlement of the structure can be stated as follows.

$$\text{Find } \mathbf{X} = \begin{Bmatrix} b \\ d \end{Bmatrix} \text{ which minimizes} \quad (2.0)$$

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = h(b,d) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{Subject to the constraints} \quad \delta_s(\mathbf{X}) \leq \delta_{\max}; b \geq 0; d \geq 0 \quad (2.1.1)$$

where δ_s is the settlement of the footing. Such problems are called *parameter or static optimization problems*.

It may be noted that, for this particular example, the length of the footing (l), the loads P_1 and P_2 and the distance between the loads are assumed to be constant and the required optimization is achieved by varying b and d . (Kumar, 2014).

(ii) In the second category of problems, the objective is to find a set of design parameters, which are all continuous functions of some other parameter that minimizes an objective function subject to a set of constraints. If the cross sectional dimensions of the rectangular footings are allowed to vary along its length as shown in Fig 3.1 (b), the optimization problem can be stated as :

$$\text{Find } \mathbf{X}(t) = \begin{Bmatrix} b(t) \\ d(t) \end{Bmatrix} \text{ which minimizes} \quad (2.2)$$

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = g(b(t), d(t)) \quad (2.3)$$

Subject to the constraints

$$\delta_s(\mathbf{X}(t)) \leq \delta_{\max} \quad 0 \leq t \leq l \quad (2.3.1)$$

$$b(t) \geq 0 \quad 0 \leq t \leq l \quad (2.4)$$

$$d(t) \geq 0 \quad 0 \leq t \leq l \quad (2.5)$$

The length of the footing (l) the loads P_1 and P_2 , the distance between the loads are assumed to be constant and the required optimization is achieved by varying b and d along the length l . (Kumar2014).

Here the design variables are functions of the length parameter t . this type of problem, where each design variable is a function of one or more parameters, is known as *trajectory or dynamic optimization problem*.

Figure 1 (a)

Figure 1 (b)

2.1.3 Classification Based on the Physical Structure of the Problem

Based on the physical structure, optimization problems are classified as optimal control and non-optimal control problems.

(i) Optimal Control Problems

An *optimal control* (OC) problem is a mathematical programming problem involving a number of stages, where each stage evolves from the preceding stage in a prescribed manner. It is defined by two types of

variables: the control or design and state variables. The *control variables* define the system and controls how one stage evolves into the next. The *state variables* describe the behavior or status of the system at any stage. The problem is to find a set of control variables such that the total objective function (also known as the performance index, PI) over all stages is minimized, subject to a set of constraints on the control and state variables. An OC problem can be stated as follows:

$$\text{Find } X \text{ which minimizes } f(X) = \sum_{i=1}^l f_i(x_i, y_i) \tag{2.6}$$

Subject to the constraints

$$q_i(x_i, y_i) + y_i = y_{i+1} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, l \tag{2.6.1}$$

$$g_j(x_j) \leq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, l \tag{2.6.2}$$

$$h_k(y_k) \leq 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, l \tag{2.6.3}$$

Where x_i is the i th control variable, y_i is the i th state variable, and f_i is the contribution of the i th stage to the total objective function. g_j , h_k , and q_i are the functions of x_j, y_j, x_k, y_k and x_i and y_i , respectively, and l is the total number of states. The control and state variables x_i and y_i can be vectors in some cases.

(ii) Problems which are not *optimal control problems* are called *non-optimal control problems*.

2.1.4 Classification Based on the Nature of the Equations Involved

Based on the nature of equations for the objective function and the constraints, optimization problems can be

classified as linear, nonlinear, geometric and quadratic programming problems. The classification is very useful from a computational point of view since many predefined special methods are available for effective solution of a particular type of problem.

(i) Linear Programming Problem

If the objective function and all the constraints are ‘linear’ functions of the design variables, the optimization problem is called a *linear programming problem* (LPP). A linear programming problem is often stated in the standard form:

$$\text{Find } \mathbf{X} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} \tag{2.7}$$

Which maximizes $f(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i$ (2.7.1)

Subject to the constraints

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} x_i = b_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{2.7.2}$$

$$x_i \geq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{2.7.3}$$

where

$c_i, a_{ij},$ and b_j are constants.

(ii) Nonlinear Programming Problem

If any of the functions among the objectives and constraint functions is nonlinear, the problem is called a *nonlinear programming (NLP) problem*. This is the most general form of a programming problem and all other problems can be considered as special cases of the NLP problem.

(iii) Geometric Programming Problem

A *geometric programming (GMP) problem* is one in which the objective function and constraints are expressed as polynomials in $\mathbf{X}$. A function $h(\mathbf{X})$ is called apolynomial (with m terms) if h can be expressed as

$$h(x) = c_1 x_1^{a_{11}} x_2^{a_{21}} \dots x_n^{a_{n1}} + c_2 x_1^{a_{12}} x_2^{a_{22}} \dots x_n^{a_{n2}} + \dots + c_m x_1^{a_{1m}} x_2^{a_{2m}} \dots x_n^{a_{nm}} \tag{2.8}$$

where

$c_j (j = 1, \Lambda, m)$ and $a_{ij} (i = 1, \Lambda, n \text{ and } j = 1, \Lambda, m)$ are constants with $c_j \geq 0$ and $x_i \geq 0$ Thus GMP problems can

be posed as follows:

Find $\mathbf{X}$ which minimizes

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_0} c_j \left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{a_{ij}} \right), c_j > 0, x_i > 0 \tag{2.9}$$

subject to

$$g_k(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_k} a_{jk} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{q_{ijk}} \right) > 0, \quad a_{jk} > 0, x_i > 0, k = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{2.9.1}$$

where N_0 and N_k denote the number of terms in the objective function and in the k^{th} constraint function, respectively.

(iv) Quadratic Programming Problem

A quadratic programming problem is the best behaved nonlinear programming problem with a quadratic

objective function and linear constraints and is concave (for maximization problems). It can be solved by suitably modifying the linear programming techniques. It is usually formulated as follows:

$$F(\mathbf{X}) = C + \sum_{i=1}^n q_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n Q_{ij} x_i x_j \tag{2.10}$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}x_i = b \tag{2.10.1}$$

$$j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$x_i \geq 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where

c, q_i, Q_{ij}, a_{ij} , and b_j are constants.

2.1.5 Classification Based on the Permissible Values of the Decision Variables

Under this classification, objective functions can be classified as integer and real-valued programming problems.

(i) Integer Programming Problem

If some or all of the design variables of an optimization problem are restricted to take only integer (or discrete) values, the problem is called an *integer programming problem*. For example, the optimization is to find number of articles needed for an operation with least effort. Thus, minimization of the effort required for the operation being the objective, the decision variables, i.e. the number of articles used can take only integer values. Other restrictions on minimum and maximum number of usable resources may be imposed.

(ii) Real-Valued Programming Problem

A real-valued problem is that in which it is sought to minimize or maximize a real function by systematically choosing the values of real variables from within an allowed set. When the allowed set contains only real values, it is called a real-valued programming problem.

2.1.6 Classification Based on Deterministic Nature of the Variables

$$f_1(x_1), f_2(x_2), \dots, f_n(x_n), \text{ i.e.}$$

$$f(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x_i) \tag{2.11}$$

and separable programming problem can be expressed in standard form as :

Find X which

$$\text{minimizes } f(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(x_i) \tag{2.12}$$

subject to

$$g_j(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij}(x_i) \leq b_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{2.12.1}$$

where

b_j is a constant.

Under this classification, optimization problems can be classified as deterministic or stochastic programming problems.

(i) Stochastic Programming Problem

In this type of an optimization problem, some or all the design variables are expressed probabilistically (non-deterministic or stochastic). For example estimates of life span of structures which have probabilistic inputs of the concrete strength and load capacity is a stochastic programming problem as one can only estimate stochastically the life span of the structure.

(ii) Deterministic Programming Problem

In this type of problems all the design variables are deterministic.

2.1.7 Classification Based on Separability of the Functions

Based on this classification, optimization problems can be classified as separable and non-separable programming problems based on the separability of the objective and constraint functions.

(i) Separable Programming Problems

In this type of a problem the objective function and the constraints are separable. A function is said to be *separable* if it can be expressed as the sum of n single-variable functions,

2.1.8 Classification Based on the Number of Objective Functions

Under this classification, objective functions can be classified as single-objective and multi-objective programming problems.

(i) Single-Objective Programming Problem in which there is only a single objective function.

(ii) Multi-Objective Programming Problem

A multi-objective programming problem can be stated as follows:

$$\text{Find } \mathbf{X} \text{ which minimizes } f_1(\mathbf{X}), f_2(\mathbf{X}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{X}) \tag{2.13}$$

Subject to

$$g_j(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

where $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k$ denote the objective functions to be minimized simultaneously.

For example in some design problems one might have to minimize the cost and weight of the structural member for economy and, at the same time, maximize the load carrying capacity under the given constraints. (Kumar,2014).

associated with a branch of knowledge. Typically, it encompasses concepts such as paradigm, theoretical model, phases and quantitative or qualitative techniques. Note that a methodology does not set out to provide solutions to the problem

III. METHODOLOGY

Methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods applied to a field of study. It comprises the theoretical analysis of the body of methods and principles

3.1 Steepest Descent Method

This method is also known as conjugate direction method.

Move in the direction of steepest ascent. Compute the slope of the function at the local point. From this obtain the best direction to move. Hill Climbing scheme.

Figure 2(a)

At next iteration,

Figure 2(b)

And, again at next iteration,

Figure 2(c)

Looking into the process from the beginning till the ascent is complete; it looks like the following on a contour plot

Figure 3

3.2 Steepest Descent Algorithm

Choose a starting point x_k . Find the local gradient of the function at this point, i.e. obtain $\nabla f|_{x_k}$.

Move in the direction of the gradient and select the next evaluation point to be

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \lambda \nabla f|_{x_k} \tag{3.0}$$

Obtain λ that maximizes $f(x_{k+1})$. Continue the process till convergence is realized. This is Hill climbing scheme. The above algorithm is for a multivariate function.

To minimize a univariate function by Steepest Descent Method, we start at some point x_0 and at k update the algorithm of the Steepest Descent Method for a univariate function is given below:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \delta x \tag{3.1}$$

where $\delta x = -\alpha \frac{df}{dx}$ and α is regarded as the step size.

A wrong step size α may not reach convergence, so a careful selection of the step size is important. Too large will diverge; too small it will take long a long time to converge. The best way is to choose a fixed step size that will assure convergence wherever you start Steepest Descent.

Now, the formula for the Steepest Descent Method in this case is:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - \alpha \frac{df}{dx} \tag{3.2}$$

3.3 Newton’s Method

Newton’s method is a general procedure that can be applied in many diverse situations. When specialized to the problem of locating a zero of real-valued function of a real variable, it is often called Newton-Raphson iteration. In general, Newton’s method is faster than the bisection method and Fixed-Point iteration since its convergence is quadratic rather than linear. Once the quadratic becomes

effective, that is, the values of Newton’s method sequence are sufficiently close to the root, the convergence is so rapid that only a few more values are needed. Unfortunately, the method is not guaranteed always to convergence. Newton’s method is often combined with other slower method in a hybrid method that is numerically globally convergence.

Suppose that we have a function f whose zeros are to be determined numerically. Let r be a zero of $f(x)$ and let x be an approximation to r . If f'' exists and is continuous, then by Taylor’s Theorem,

$$0 = f(r) = f(x + h) = f(x) + hf'(x) + o(h^2), \tag{3.3}$$

Where $h = r - x$. If h is small (that is, x is near r), then it is reasonable to ignore the $o(h^2)$ term and solve the remaining equation for h . If we do this, the result is $h = -f(x)/f'(x)$. If x is an approximation to r , then $x - f(x)/f'(x)$ should be r . Newton’s method begins with an estimate x_0 of r and then defines inductively

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{f(x_n)}{f'(x_n)} \quad (n \geq 0) \tag{3.4}$$

3.3.1 Newton’s Algorithm

x_0 = Initial guess

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{f(x_n)}{f'(x_n)}, \text{ for } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{3.5}$$

Before examining the theoretical basis for Newton’s method, let’s give a graphical interpretation of it. From the description already given, we can say that Newton’s method involves linearizing the function. That is,

f was replaced by a linear function. The usual way of doing this is to replace f by the first two terms in the Taylor series. Thus, if

$$f(x) = f(c) + f'(c)(x - c) + \frac{1}{2!} f''(c)(x - c)^2 + \dots \tag{3.6}$$

Then the linearization (at c) produces the linear function

$$l(x) = f(c) + f'(c)(x - c). \tag{3.7}$$

Note that l is a good approximation to f in the vicinity of c , and in fact we have $l(c) = f(c)$ and $l'(c) = f'(c)$. Thus, the linear function has the same value and the same slope as fit the point c . So in Newton’s method we are constructing the target line to f at a point near r , and finding where the target line intersects the x -axis.

4.1 Minimization of the Optimization Problem

In this section, there will be a comparison between the two unconstrained optimization methods. We use the two methods to solve an optimization problem. As we know, the two unconstrained optimization methods to be used to solve the optimization problem are Steepest Descent Method and Newton’s Method.

The optimization problem to be solved is a univariate function. The function to be optimized will be minimized is given below:

IV. DATA PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

$$f(x) = 72x^3 - 234x^2 + 241x - 78 \tag{4.0}$$

4.2 Steepest Descent Method

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + \delta x, \quad \text{for } k = 0, 1, 2 \dots \tag{4.1}$$

Using the Steepest Descent method to solve the above function, we are going to use the formula for univariate functions which is:

where $\delta x = -\alpha \frac{df}{dx}$, therefore $x_{k+1} = x_k - \alpha \frac{df}{dx_k}$ (4.2)
 $f(x) = 72x^3 - 234x^2 + 241x - 78$

The derivative of $f(x)$ is easily computed:

$$\frac{df}{dx} = 216x^2 - 468x + 241 \tag{4.3}$$

Then we need to choose an initial point for $x_0=10$ and $\alpha = 0.00005$

When $k = 0$ then,

$$x_1 = x_0 - \alpha \frac{df}{dx}(x_0) = 10 - 0.00005[216(10)^2 - 468(10) + 241]$$

= 9.14195

Therefore, $x_1 = 9.14195$

Since $x_1 = 9.14195$ and $\alpha \frac{df}{dx}(x_0) = 0.858050$, we continue to iterate by substituting x_1 to the Steepest Descent formula as $k = 1$ to obtain $x_2 = 8.441209$ and so

on until we get to the iterate at which it converges. The complete iteration sequence is given in the table below:

4.2.1 Iterates of Steepest Descent Method

k	x_k	$\alpha \frac{df}{dx}$	x_{k+1}
0	10.00000	0.858050	9.141950
1	9.141950	0.700741	8.441209
2	8.441209	0.584069	7.857140
3	7.857140	0.494927	7.362213
4	7.362213	0.425158	6.937055
5	6.937055	0.369448	6.567607
6	6.567607	0.324209	6.243398
7	6.243398	0.286939	5.956459
8	5.956459	0.255846	5.700613
9	5.700613	0.229623	5.470990
10	5.47099	0.207292	5.263698
11	5.263698	0.188109	5.075589
12	5.075589	0.167105	4.908484
13	4.908484	0.157398	4.751086
14	4.751086	0.144661	4.606425

15	4.606425	0.133426	4.472999
16	4.472999	0.123465	4.349534
17	4.349534	0.114590	4.234944
18	4.234944	0.106648	4.128296
19	4.128296	1.064130	3.064166
20	3.064166	1.053321	2.010845
21	2.010845	0.008666	2.002179
22	2.002179	0.008325	1.993686
23	1.993686	0.008325	1.985361
24	1.985361	0.008113	1.9772480
25	1.977248	0.008005	1.969243
26	1.969243	0.007851	1.961392
27	1.961255	0.007691	1.96034

Source: Research field study, 2019

The Steepest Descent method converges to $x = 1.96$ at the 27th iteration.

4.3 Newton’s Method

Using the univariate formula of Newton’s method to solve the optimization problem that was solved using Steepest Descent method.

$$f(x) = 72x^3 - 234x^2 + 241x - 78 \tag{4.5}$$

$f'(x)$ is also known as the derivative of $f(x)$ which is:

$$f'(x) = 216x^2 - 468x + 241 \tag{4.6}$$

Let’s now assume an initial point $x_0 = 10$

When $k = 0$ then,

$$x_1 = x_0 - \frac{f(x_0)}{f'(x_0)}$$

$$= 10 - \frac{[72(10)^3 - 234(10)^2 + 241(10) - 78]}{[216(10)^2 - 468(10) + 241]}$$

$$= 7.032108$$

The value for $x_1 = 7.032108$ and $\frac{f(x_0)}{f'(x_0)} = 2.978923$. As discussed in Steepest Descent method, we continue to iterate by substituting x_1 to the Newton’s formula as $k = 1$ to obtain $x_2 = 5.055679$ and so on until

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - \frac{f(x_k)}{f'(x_k)}, \text{ for } k = 0, 1, 2 \dots \tag{4.4}$$

Thus, algorithm make progression as long as $f'(x_k) > 0$. The algorithm above determines its next estimate.

Now, we consider the function to be minimized:

we get to the rate at which it converges. The complete iteration sequence is given in the table below:

4.3.1 The iterates of Newton’s Method

k	x_k	$\frac{f(x_k)}{f'(x_k)}$	x_{k+1}
0	10.000000	2.978923	7.0321080
1	7.0321080	1.976429	5.055679
2	5.055679	1.314367	3.741312
3	3.741312	0.871358	2.869995
4	2.869995	0.573547	2.296405
5	2.296405	0.371252	1.925154

6	1.925154	0.230702	1.694452
7	1.694452	0.128999	1.565453
8	1.565453	0.054156	1.511296
9	1.511296	0.0108640	1.500432
10	1.500432	0.000431	1.500001

Source: Research field study, 2019

After the iteration, our convergence to $x = 1.50$ at the 5th iteration.

Now considering the iteration s of the two methods, we noticed that the rate at which Steepest Descent uses to converge is slow because it was at the 27th iterate it got its convergence. While for Newton's the rate of convergence is fast in the sense that it converged at the 10th iteration and it is more accurate.

Previous researchers have also concluded that Newton's method is faster and more accurate than other optimization methods.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, the researchers tried to examine the rate at which the two unconstrained optimization method will converge and the accuracy of the methods.

The objective of this research work is to find out which method is more accurate to getting to the convergence point. It was observed that the Steepest Descent method took a longer time before it got to the point of convergence while for that of Newton's method, the rate at which it got to the point of convergence was far faster and more accurate than Steepest Descent method.

This paper work was aimed at studying the convergence of two unconstrained optimization methods using the two methods to solve the same optimization problem. It highlights the significance of the study, limitations and definition of some terms, which formed the parameters for the research to work with. It also focuses on the basics of optimization methods, types of problem and what method could be used in solving them. The two unconstrained optimization methods chosen were used to solve an optimization method, checking their convergence point and their rate of convergence.

5.1 Recommendation

1. It is recommended that Newton's method should be used preferred to Steepest Descent method for easy computation and accurate solution.
2. There should be a fixed value for the step size in Steepest Descent method.

3. This project work is recommended to those interested in carrying out optimization subject to no constraint. The right method should be used depending on the problem definition and target goal.

REFERENCES

- [1] Charnes .A. & Cooper W.W. (1962). *Programming with linear fractional functional*. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/nav.3800100123>.
- [2] Bradley S.P. & Frey S.C. (1974). Fractional programming with homogeneous functions. *Operations Research*, 22(2), 350-357.
- [3] Dr. Binay Kuma. (2014). *Advanced method for solution of constraint optimization problems*. Available at: <https://rd.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-981-13-8196-6>.
- [4] Holt C. C, Modigliani F, Muth J. F, & Simon H. A. (1960). *Planning production, inventories, and work-force*, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- [5] John W. Chinneck. (2012). *Practical optimization: A gentle introduction*. Available at: <http://www.sce.carleton.ca/faculty/chinneck/po.html>.
- [6] Kuhn, H. & A. Tucker. (1950). *Nonlinear programming*. Available at: <http://web.math.ku.dk/~moller/undervisning/MASO2010/kuhntucker1950.pdf>.
- [7] Slater M. (1950). *Lagrange multipliers revisited: A contribution to nonlinear programming*. Available at: <https://cowles.yale.edu/sites/default/files/files/pub/cdp/m-0403.pdf>.
- [8] White L. S. (2018). *Mathematical programming models for determining freshman scholarship offers*. Forgotten Books.
- [9] Winters P. R. (1962). Constrained inventory rules for production smoothing. *Management Science*, 8(4).
- [10] Van SlykeR. M. & Wets R. J. (1968). *A duality theory for abstract mathematical programs with applications to optimal control theory*. Available at: <https://apps.dtic.mil/docs/citations/AD0663661>.